

Microwave-induced synthesis of optically active lactones from β -lactams by acid-assisted ring cleavage

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Microwave-induced acid-assisted regioselective and chiral synthesis of 5-membered lactones from β -lactams is described.

Keywords: Microwave, β -lactam, regioselective, lactone, ring cleavage.

Introduction

A number of antibiotics are clinically used for the past many years. However, the use of β -lactams as clinically active antibiotics is the most common because of their effectiveness and minimum toxicity¹. Moreover, this 4-membered cyclic amide serves as the key starting material for the preparation a number of heterocycles². Because of the ring size and highly strained amide bond, numerous chemical modifications are permitted on β -lactams and therefore, many open chain and cyclic compounds with nitrogen atom are prepared. The β -lactam rings are extremely sensitive in the presence of acids, bases, enzymes, oxidizing and reducing agents. The sensitivity of the ring is exploited by scientists for a variety of reasons, e.g. for the synthesis of other structures. However, the cleavage of the ring depends on the nature and concentration of the acidic or basic medium. In this paper, a simple microwave-assisted method for the regioselective preparation of 5-membered lactones by acid-induced cleavage of the amide bond of the β -lactams and subsequent *in situ* cyclization with a secondary hydroxyl group is described³.

Results

Optically active β -lactam **1** starting from D-mannitol de-

rivative was prepared⁴. The ketal group was deprotected to diol **2** under acidic condition. Microwave-induced reaction of **2** with aqueous acidic solution (TFA) afforded a 5-membered lactone **3** instead of 6-membered lactone **4** in good yield (Scheme 1). It is interesting to note that the intermediate hydroxy acid derivative preferentially cyclizes to a 5-membered ring although this type of cyclization takes place with a secondary hydroxyl group. A 6-membered ring formation through a cyclization of primary hydroxyl group with the acid is not the course of the overall process (Scheme 2). The entire process that includes deprotection of the ketal, ring cleavage of the amide and cyclization to the lactone occurs extremely spontaneously. The deprotection of the ketal is assumed as the first step of this sequence considering the sensitivity of this group compared to the amide linkage. In principle, the product would remain the same even if the amide bond breaks faster than the ketal group. No lactone would be formed unless both the ketal and amide bond rupture to their corresponding diol and amino acid derivatives. These bond breakage methods are possible due to the highly acidic conditions of the reaction and microwave irradiation. No lactone is formed under this condition if microwave radiation is not used. This suggests that a combination of microwave along with acidic conditions is required for the success

1a R¹ = Ph 1b R¹ = PMP 1c R¹ = *p*-methylphenyl R = acetyl, methyl, phenyl.

Reagents and condition: a) TFA (0.5M), THF: H₂O (3:1), 50°C, MWI, 2-3 min, 80-90%.

Scheme 1. Microwave induced trifluoroacetic acid mediated synthesis of 2,3,4-trisubstituted butanolide from β -lactam.

Table 1

Entry	R	R ¹	Conditions			T (°C)	3	4	Yield ^a (%)
			Solvent	Base	Time (min)				
1	Acetyl	Ph	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	2	50	3a	4a	80
2	Acetyl	PMP	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	2	50	3b	4b	90
3	Acetyl	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	2	50	3c	4c	85
4	Methyl	Ph	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	2	50	3d	4d	80
5	Methyl	PMP	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	2	50	3e	4e	85
6	Methyl	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	3	50	3f	4f	80
7	Phenyl	Ph	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	3	50	3g	4g	85
8	Phenyl	PMP	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	2	50	3h	4h	85
9	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	THF:H ₂ O	TFA (0.5 M)	3	50	3i	4i	80

^aIsolated yield after column chromatography.

of this reaction. The use of weaker acid (*p*-toluene sulfonic acid) is capable of doing deprotection of the ketal. However, it is not possible to break the ring using a higher proportion of this acid. Bismuth nitrate is able to form the diol, but not the lactone. This type of selectivity among the acids indicates not only their strength but also their affinity toward certain functional groups in a molecule. In the present study, a number of β -lactams with diverse groups at -N, and C-3 center is used with success. It is important to note that ester and ether groups tolerate under this reaction conditions. Further-

more, the stereochemistry of all stereogenic centers in the products remains unaltered.

Mechanistically, the formation of **3** can be explained by protonation of the carbonyl group of the β -lactams of vicinal diol **2** to form **2B**. The structure **B** then breaks to **C** which on protonation generates amino acid alcohol **2C**. This highly unstable intermediate follows exclusively route "a" to produce **3** instead of route "b" (Scheme 2). This process is facilitated by microwave irradiation.

Experimental

In a 125 mL Erlenmeyer Flask, THF-water-TFA (2 mL) was added to β -lactams **2** (1 mmol) and the reaction mixture was irradiated for 2–3 min in a domestic microwave at low power level. After being cooled to room temperature, dichloromethane (20 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and it was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%, 5 mL), brine (5 mL). The organic extracts were then evaporated and passed through a short column of silica gel (5 g) using ethylacetate and hexanes (40:60) as the solvent to afford the pure product **3**.

Scheme 2. Mechanistic route for the synthesis of butanolide under acidic condition.

Conclusions

Optically active highly functionalized 5-membered lactone from β -lactams ring cleavage reaction is prepared by an easy route through microwave-induced reaction. Chemical alterations of lactone **3** are feasible for the synthesis of optically active molecules. This reaction is extremely rapid and regioselective. Three important reactions (deprotection of the ketal, ring cleavage of the ring and lactonisation) take place simultaneously in a single flask with a single reagent and within a few minutes. The products obtained from this study have multiple chiral centers and functional groups (lactone, primary alcohol, protected ester/ether and aromatic amine). It is important to maintain the conditions precisely. In some instances, C-3 acetoxy group can be hydrolyzed to an alcohol. One of the notable observations of this reaction is the formation of a 5-membered lactone instead of 6-membered lactone. Although the chemical stability of the corresponding 5- and 6-membered lactones is not determined, clearly this study is fascinating. The primary alcohol of the diol should be more reactive to the generated carboxylic acid through ring cleavage reaction to form the 6-membered lactone. The formation of 5-membered lactone in this study, therefore, indicates that it is not only the stability or the reac-

tivity of the functional groups, there may be other contributing factors that can dominate in certain examples and this can produce an unexpected product predominantly or exclusively.

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